

FREEDOM OF OPINION, EXPRESSION AND THE PRESS IN ISLAMIC LAW

حرية الرأي والتعبير والصحافة في الشريعة الإسلامية

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Abstract

This study (*Freedom of Opinion, Expression and the Press in Islamic Sharia*) dealt with the subject of the press in: Exposing the press, its freedoms and controls, and the links of the press. most aspects of human, natural and cosmic activity; It was worth studying all their aspects to clarify the position of Sharia and the law on them and their rulings on them. There is no doubt about the necessity and necessity of submitting them to their controls to ensure optimum benefit from them, as they are among the services that are indispensable in our contemporary time. Topics related to the press today are among the topics worthy of study and care, as the press occupies a large and influential space in various fields of life. The conditions and rights of journalists are of great importance in the field of public international law and international humanitarian law, in many respects. In times of peace, journalists play a role in educating society, exposing flaws and corruption, and reviewing events taking place in the country or in other regions of the world. International law has granted journalists protection and the possibility of free expression and monitoring of the facts that occur here and there as they are, by granting him the right to express what he sees or observes, and what he concludes in the sphere of his presence and the sphere of his activity, and this right is enshrined in the framework of human rights. On the other hand, journalists receive the attention of international humanitarian law as civilians working in situations of civil or international armed conflicts, and it gives them the necessary protection to carry out their role in transmitting and disseminating information about current events, especially with regard to violations and crimes that may occur during those conflicts. I would like to point out the subject of international legal protection that the journalist enjoys. This protection is enjoyed by him as a civilian during peace and in the arenas of armed conflicts around the world. Therefore, this research will focus on the system of customary legal rules and the convention that defines the general framework for the protection of the journalist and enable him to play his role in receiving and transmitting news. This study was based on the extrapolation of the issues in which the opinions of scholars varied according to the multiplicity of factors related to the edge, according to an applied analytical methodology.

Keywords: freedom of expression, edge, Sharia, Islamic law.

ملخص البحث

تناولت هذه الدراسة (حرية الرأي والتعبير والصحافة في الشريعة الإسلامية) موضوع الصحافة في: تعرض للصحافة وحرّياتها وضوابطها، وروابط الصحافة: وقد توصلت الدراسة إلى أن الإعلام عمومًا والصحافة خصوصًا قد أخذًا حيزًا كبيرًا ومهمًا في أبرز ميادين الحياة المعاصرة خصوصًا الإعلام الاجتماعي المفتوح المصادر، وطالًا معظم جوانب النشاط الإنساني والطبيعي والكوني؛ فكان جديرًا أن تدرس كل جوانبها لبيان موقف الشريعة والقانون منها وأحكامها فيهما؛ ولا جدال في وجوب وضرورة خضوعهما لضوابطهما لضمان استفادة مثلى منهما باعتبارهما من الخدمات التي لا غنى عنها في زمننا المعاصر. وتعد الموضوعات المتعلقة بالصحافة في وقتنا الحاضر من الموضوعات الجديرة بالدراسة والعناية، حيث يشغل الصحافة حيزًا كبيرًا ومؤثرًا في مختلف ميادين الحياة. وتحظى أوضاع الصحفيين وحقوقهم بأهمية كبيرة في مجال القانون الدولي العام والقانون الدولي الإنساني، وذلك من عدة نواحٍ؛ ففي زمن السلم يلعب الصحفيون دورًا في توعية المجتمع وكشف مواطن الخلل والفساد واستعراض الأحداث التي تجري في البلد أو في مناطق العالم الأخرى. وقد أسبغ القانون الدولي على الصحفيين الحماية وإمكانية التعبير الحر ورصد الوقائع التي تحدث هنا وهناك كما هي، من خلال منحه الحق في التعبير عما يعاينه أو يلاحظه، وما يستنتجه في دائرة تواجده ودائرة نشاطه، وهذا الحق كرس في إطار حقوق الإنسان. ومن ناحية أخرى، يحظى الصحفيون باهتمام القانون الدولي الإنساني باعتبارهم أشخاصًا مدنيون يعملون في حالات النزاعات المسلحة الأهلية أو الدولية، ويمنحهم الحماية اللازمة للقيام بدورهم في نقل ونشر المعلومات حول الأحداث الجارية، خصوصًا فيما يتعلق بالانتهاكات والجرائم التي قد تحدث أثناء تلك النزاعات. وأود الإشارة إلى موضوع الحماية القانونية الدولية التي يحظى بها الصحفي، فهذه الحماية يحظى بها ك شخص مدني أثناء السلم وفي ساحات النزاعات المسلحة في مختلف أنحاء العالم، ولذلك سوف يركز هذا البحث على منظومة القواعد القانونية العرفية والاتفاقية التي تحدد الإطار العام لحماية الصحفي، وتمكنه من أداء دوره في تلقي الأخبار ونقلها. ولقد قامت هذه الدراسة على استقراء المسائل التي تعددت آراء العلماء فيها تبعًا لتعدد العوامل المتعلقة بالحقافة وذلك وفق منهجية تطبيقية تحليلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: حرية، التعبير، الحافة، الشريعة، الإسلامية.

Freedom and Expression:

Islamic Sharia has given appropriate importance to freedom of opinion and freedom of expression as one of the basic foundations of many jurisprudential and fundamental rules, as this freedom is one of the main reasons for revealing the facts of matters, and the scholars of origins emphasize that freedom in addition to justice and facilitation are among the main general purposes of Islamic law.

Indeed, some scholars have established a hierarchical theory of changing the levels of Sharia, making these three objectives the top of the objective hierarchy and considering them as an original branch of the other levels of objectives such as justice, freedom and equality. Fundamentalists and jurists on them and considered them the purposes of Sharia and classified them into necessities, needs and improvements, that is, these principles: freedom, justice and facilitation, "the above-mentioned objectives" is a basis from which the objectives of the Sharia branch.

This, while others considered the purposes of justice, freedom, equality, dignity, and the right of expression as ramifications, derivations, and activation of the connotations and meanings of the five colleges concerned with preserving life, religion, money, offspring and honor.

After expressing an opinion was reprehensible and rejected under the pre-Islamic laws of most peoples, the Islamic Sharia came to recognize this right for all segments of society, and thus freedom of opinion finds its legislative support for the first time in history and to open the door to all that will come later in terms of laws, legislation and human revolutions that restore *إِلَى الْخَيْرِ وَيَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ*، وقوله تعالى: *(الَّذِينَ إِن مَكَّنَّاهُمْ فِي الْأَرْضِ أَقَامُوا الصَّلَاةَ وَآتَوُا الزَّكَاةَ وَأَمَرُوا بِالْمَعْرُوفِ* And they forbade what is evil, and to God belongs the end of all affairs.

Whereas, the Holy Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, was not satisfied with inviting the public to express their opinions freely; Rather, he would urge his companions to practice it among themselves and with him personally, so he would seek their opinions on public affairs and private interests, and everyone would give his opinion without hesitation or fear.

The evidence for this is what happened in the Battle of Badr when the Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, came to the nearest water from the Badr Valley and descended there. Al-Habbab bin al-Mundhir came to him and said to him: O Messenger of God, is this a house that God has sent you down to, or is it opinion, war and intrigue? The Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said to him: "Rather, it is opinion, war, and intrigue." Al-Habbab indicated to him that he should go down in a place other than the one in which he had descended, so the Messenger accepted this opinion from him and turned to the place referred to by Al-Habbab and said: "You have indicated the opinion." The Rightly Guided Caliphs and Muslim princes after them proceeded to encourage the opinion, accept advice from those who gave it to them, and retract their opinion whenever they found correctness and wisdom in the opinion of others.

And when Omar Ibn Al-Khattab assumed the caliphate on the authority of Abu Bakr Al-Siddiq, may God be pleased with them both, he addressed the people with his famous sermon: "If you see a crookedness in me, straighten me. في الأمة يمكنهم الجهر بالحق بحرية. ومرة أخرى خطب الخليفة عمر بن الخطاب رضي الله عنه في الناس طالباً عدم الزيادة في المهر عن أربعمئة درهم، فتعترضه A slander and a manifest sin." *إِنْ أَرَدْتُمْ اسْتِبْدَالَ زَوْجٍ مَكَانَ زَوْجٍ وَآتَيْتُمْ إِخْدَاهُنَّ قِطْرًا فَلَا تَأْخُذُوا مِنْهُ شَيْئًا أَنَا أَخَذْتُهُ* Omar did not denounce it, but immediately returned to the truth, saying: "Umar made a mistake and a woman was injured." He was between him and a hadith man, and the man said to him: Fear God, Commander of the Faithful. God? Then Omar said to him: "Let him say it to me. Yes, what he said, there is no good in you if you do not say it, and there is no good in us if we do not accept it."

Among these famous evidence, and many others, and there is no room for further discussion in this regard, it becomes clear to what extent the Caliph Omar Ibn Al-Khattab, may God be pleased with him, was keen to accept the opinion of others, take it and respect it, and confirm the foundations of this right that the Prophet, peace be upon him, established and works by him And after him there were caliphs and princes, and history books are full of countless witnesses like this, even in the most difficult eras, and with the most severe and stubbornness of the caliphs, sultans and princes. At the same time, he was patient and gentle in listening to criticism and the opinions of his citizens, and in his judgment and decisions. Islamic philosophy and theology have been concerned with freedom of expression and made it one of the basic human rights, and religion has stood alongside the freedom to express and express opinion without coercion or pressure, and freedom in the Islamic system is a means of worship, where a person is loyal to his Lord free to take his opinions and positions, which is The essence of Islam and the necessity of believing in it, and it has been a tangible reality since the era of the Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, and the Rightly Guided Caliphs.

The press:

Many researchers point out that the Islamic press system is distinguished by its characteristics and features *قل نظيرها في النظم الصحافية الوضعية، وهي مأخوذة من أساس ديني وشرعي أصيل وأساسي في الإسلام هو (لَا إِكْرَاهَ فِي الدِّينِ قَدْ تَبَيَّنَ الرُّشْدُ مِنَ الْغَيِّ) قَمَنْ يَكْفُرْ بِالطَّاغُوتِ وَيُؤْمِنَ بِاللَّهِ فَقَدِ اسْتَمْسَكَ بِالْعُرْوَةِ الْوُثْقَى لَا انْفِصَامَ لَهَا وَاللَّهُ سَمِيعٌ عَلِيمٌ* As it was taken from the purposes of the tolerant Islamic Sharia, such as moderation, because Islam does not say With the absolute group or the absolute individuality,

- 9) The relative and remarkable success in protecting media and journalistic work in various countries of the world was achieved through unifying the professional work rules for media professionals and journalists, including protection and keeping pace with all stages of media and journalistic work, starting from receiving information and ending with its dissemination to public opinion.

Margins:

- Al-Kubaisi, Saad Abdul Rahman Faraj, *The Purposes of Sharia in the Prophetic Sunnah*, Ph.D. thesis, Dar al-Salaam, 1438 AH / 2017, p. 730.
- () Al-Alwani, Taha Jaber, *Maqasid al-Shariah*, Dar al-Fikr, Damascus, 1422 AH / 2002 AD, pp. 82-83.
- () Al-Kubaisi, Saad Abdul Rahman Faraj, *The Purposes of Sharia in the Prophetic Sunnah*, previous reference, p. 102.
- () Surah Al Imran: 104.
- () Surat Al-Hajj Verse: 41.
- () Al-Aqib, Adel Mahjoub Ahmed, *Freedom of the Press from an Islamic Perspective*, Faculty of Arts - International University of Africa, 2012. p. 83.
- () Al-Duaij, Fahd Abdulaziz, *Security and Media in the Islamic State*, Arab Center for Security Studies and Training, Riyadh, 1406 AH 1986 AD, pp. 236-237.
- () Al-Habbab bin Al-Mundhir Al-Khazraji, a great companion of the Ansar, who witnessed with the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, all the scenes. He said: "I am its touching emblem, and its desirable fragrance. From us is a prince, and from you is a prince." He died, may God be pleased with him, during the caliphate of Omar Ibn Al-Khattab, and he was over fifty years old, and he had a son Khashram and a beautiful mother, their mother Zainab bint Saifi bin Sakhr. Ibn Saad, Muhammad bin Saad bin Mani' Al-Hashemi, (230 AH) *al-Tabaqaat al-Kubra*, 3/567, investigation: Muhammad Abdul Qadir Atta, Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya, Beirut, first edition, 1410 AH - 1990 AD.
- () Al-Hakim, Al-Mustadrak, previous reference, Hadith No.: 5801, Ibn Saad, *Al-Tabaqa Al-Kubra*, previous reference, 3/567, Al-Bayhaqi, *Evidence of Prophethood*, previous reference, 3/31, Ibn Al-Atheer, *Asad Al-Ghaba*, previous reference, 1/ 665.
- () Omar bin Al-Khattab bin Nufail Al-Qurashi Al-Adawi, (40 BC - 23 AH = 584 - 644 AD), the second of the Rightly-Guided Caliphs, and the first to be called the Commander of the Faithful, embraced Islam five years before the Hijrah, witnessed the facts, and was pledged allegiance to the caliphate on the day of the death of Abu Bakr in the year 13 AH with a covenant from him. During his reign, the Levant and Iraq were conquered, and Jerusalem, the cities, Egypt and the island were opened. He is the first to put the Hijri date to the Arabs, and they dated the facts. And he took the Muslims' treasury, and ordered the construction of Basra and Kufa, and the first to write down the offices made it according to the Persian way to count the owners of the gifts and distribute the salaries to them. The Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, called him Al-Faruq, and called him Abu Hafsa. He was ivory-white, tall and well-mannered, with a bushy beard. Abu Lulu'a Fayrouz al-Farsi (Ghulam al-Mughirah bin Shu'bah) killed him by ghila, with a dagger in his side while he was in the morning prayer, and he lived after the stabbing for three nights. Books have been written about him bearing his name, such as: "Omar Ibn Al-Khattab" by Ibn Al-Jawzi, "The Genius of Omar" by Abbas Mahmoud Al-Akkad, "The History of Omar Ibn Al-Khattab" by Bashir Yamout, "Omar Ibn Al-Khattab" by Sheikh Ali Al-Tantawi and Naji Al-Tantawi, and "Al-Faruq" Omar" by Muhammad Husayn Heikal. Al-Zarkali, Al-Alam, op. reference, 5/45-46.
- () Abu Bakr Al-Siddiq, Abdullah bin Abi Quhafa Othman bin Amer bin Ka'b Al-Taymi Al-Qurashi, (51 BC - 13 AH = 573 - 634 AD), the first of the Rightly-Guided Caliphs, and the first of men to believe in the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, was born in Makkah. And he grew up as a master of the masters of Quraysh, and he was rich among their senior rulers, and he knew the lineages of the tribes, their news and their politics, and the Arabs called him the scholar of Quraysh. 11 AH and he fought the apostates and those who refrained from paying the zakat, and in his days the Levant and a section of Iraq were opened, and he was described as dreaming and compassionate to the general public, an orator, a brave hero. The duration of his caliphate was two years and three and a half months, and he died in Medina. Among the books written about him are: "Abu Bakr Al-Siddiq" by Muhammad Hussein Heikal, and "Abu Bakr Al-Siddiq" by Sheikh Ali Al-Tantawi. Al-Zarkali, Al-Alam, previous reference, 4/102.
- () Ibn al-Jawzi, Abu al-Faraj, *the virtues of the Commander of the Faithful, Omar Ibn al-Khattab*, investigation: Sayyid al-Jumaili, 2004, p. 41.
- () Surah An-Nisa: 20.
- () Ibn al-Jawzi, Abu al-Faraj, *the virtues of the Commander of the Faithful, Omar Ibn al-Khattab*, previous reference, p. 86.
- () Al-Hajjaj bin Yusuf Al-Thaqafi, (41-95 AH/661-713 AD), one of the most prominent rulers and officials in the era of the Umayyad dynasty. He was an articulate orator and a shrewd politician. He was born in the city of Taif in the Hijaz. Famous for science, wisdom, and a destination in solving problems and fatwas, Abd al-Malik ibn Marwan imitated the leadership of the army and ordered him to fight Abdullah ibn al-Zubayr in Mecca. Al-Mukhtar bin Abi Obaid Al-Thaqafi, the Kharijites' blue and yellow movements and the revolution of Abdul Rahman Al-Kindi, and in the year 83 AH he built the city of Wasit between Kufa and Basra, and the Umayyad coinage was minted and he asked Nasr bin Asim to put the dots and movements on the letters. He was a memorizer of the Qur'an, a lot of reading to him, and he urged his commanders to order the soldiers to abide by the Qur'an. He wrote to Qutayba bin Muslim al-Bahili, "Take your army by reciting the Qur'an, for it will protect your fortresses." Among his works are

- reclamation of lands, draining swamps, digging canals and canals, and digging sewage to deliver water to waste lands such as the Zabi River and the Anbar River. And he built bridges, and loaned farmers from the treasury. This is in addition to being eloquent, as Ibn Al-Ala said about him: "I have not seen more eloquent than Al-Hasan Al-Basri and Al-Hajjaj." See: Al-Amad, Ihsan Sidqi, Al-Hajjaj bin Youssef Al-Thaqafi, House of Culture, Beirut, 1973.
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 - () Fouda, Mr. Abdel Hamid, Human Rights between Legal Systems and Islamic Law, Dar Al-Fikr Al-Jamii, Alexandria, Egypt, 2003, p. 149.
 - () Al-Saleh, Muhammad bin Ahmed Saleh, Human Rights in the Qur'an and Sunnah and their Applications in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, First Edition, 1423 AH / 2002 AD, p. 33.
 - () Al-Amili, Malik Mustafa Wahbi, Intellectual and Political Freedom under Islamic Rule, Dar Al-Hadi for Printing and Publishing, Beirut - Lebanon, 1422 AH - 2002 AD, pp. 281-282.
 - () Review the research and studies of the Conference on Controlling the Use of Social Networks in Islam, organized by the Nayef bin Abdulaziz Prize for the Prophetic Sunnah and its studies in cooperation with the Islamic University of Madinah, Safar 23, 1438 AH corresponding to November 23, 2016, and his works were published in five volumes.
 - () Surat Al-Hadid: 4-5.
 - () Ibn Majah, Al-Sunan, 2/1418, Hadith No. 4245.
 - () Al-Bukhari, The Sahih Mosque, 1/6, Hadith No. 1, and Sahih Muslim, 3/1515, Hadith No. 1907.
 - () Narrated by Al-Bukhari 3/53, Hadith No.: 2051, and Muslim 3/1219, Hadith No.: 1599.
 - () Surat Al-A'raf: 33.
 - () Surat Al-Hujurat: 21.
 - () Narrated by Al-Tirmidhi, 4/350, Hadith No.: 1977.
 - () Narrated by Al-Bukhari 8/11 Hadith No. 6018, Muslim 1/68, Hadith No. 47.
 - () Surah Al-Hujurat: 6.
 - () Sahih Al-Bukhari 8/100, Hadith No. 6477, and Muslim 4/2290, Hadith No. 2988.
 - () Such as: Mustafa Dib Al-Bagha, Muhammad Salih Al-Munajjid and Salman Al-Awdah. See: Al-Zaidi, Taha Ahmed, Shariah Controls for Dealing with Social Media, Al-Bayan Magazine, Issue 374, Educational Issues, June 14, 2018.
 - () Surah Al-Ahzab: 23.
 - () Surat An-Nur: 30-31.
 - () Al-Hakim, 4/341, Hadith: 7846, and he said: An authentic hadith according to the conditions of the two sheikhs and they did not produce it, and Al-Dhahabi agreed with him.
 - () Al-Tirmidhi, 4/612, hadith number 2416, and he said: This hadith is hasan saheeh, and the narration was included by al-Bazzar in his Musnad, 4/266, hadith number 1435.
 - () Surah An-Nur: 37.
 - () Salman al-Farisi (died in the year 33 A.H.) was a great Companion, who came to the Arabian Peninsula from the Levant, and during the trip he was betrayed and sold to a Jew from Banu Qurayza. He converted to Islam after the migration, and the Prophet, peace and blessings be upon him, and the companions helped him to write to his owner until he was freed. He witnessed the Battle of the Trench, and pointed to the Muslims to dig the trench to protect the city and strengthen its defenses. He witnessed all the invasions with the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace. The Messenger, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said in his virtues: "Paradise years for three: Ali, Ammar and Salman." During the Battle of Al-Ahzab, when the immigrants and the Ansar argued about his lineage, the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said: "Salman is one of us, Ahl al-Bayt." See: Ibn Saad, Al-Tabaqat Al-Kubra, 4/61 onwards, Abu Naim, Hilyat Al-Awliya', 1/205 onwards.
 - () Abdul Razzaq, Al-Musannaf, 1/48, Hadith No. 481

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